

Studies in Chromones and Flavones. Part VII^a. Synthesis of some 3',3''' and 6, 6'6''-biflavonyls

K. P. Mathai, (Miss) B. Kanakalakshmi and Suresh Sethna

The bichalconyl derivatives, obtained from the condensation of 2,2'- and 4,4'-dimethoxy-3,3'-diformyl biphenyl with 2-hydroxy-4-methoxyacetophenone, of 2,2',6,6' and 2,2', 4,4'-tetramethoxy-3,3'-diformyl biphenyl with 2-hydroxyacetophenone and of 4,4'-dihydroxy-3,3'-diacetyl biphenyl with anisaldehyde have been converted into the corresponding biflavonyl derivatives. Some of these have also been obtained by the Ullmann reaction on the appropriate iodoflavones. Some of the chalcones and bichalconyls have been isomerised to the corresponding flavanones and biflavanonols respectively.

In an earlier communication¹ the authors described the synthesis of some biflavonyl derivatives starting with biphenyl derivatives. The work has now been extended and several new biflavonyls have been synthesised.

4, 4'-Dimethoxy-3,3'-diformyl biphenyl² on condensation with 2-hydroxy-4-methoxy acetophenone gave 2',2'''-dihydroxy-4',4'''-6,6''-tetramethoxy-3, 3''-bichalconyl derivative (Ia). It formed a diacetoxy derivative and responded to the colour reactions of a chalcone. It was converted into 6', 6'''-7,7'''-tetramethoxy-3',3'''-biflavonyl (IIa) by refluxing with selenium dioxide in amyl alcohol. The same product was also synthesised as follows:

2-Hydroxy-4-methoxy acetophenone was condensed with 2-methoxy-5-iodo benzaldehyde when 2'-hydroxy-2,4'-dimethoxy-5-iodochalcone was obtained. This was converted into 7, 2'-dimethoxy-5'-iodoflavone by heating with selenium dioxide. The iodoflavone on Ullmann reaction gave the biflavonyl described above. The iodochalcone was also converted into the corresponding flavanone by refluxing with alcoholic hydrochloric acid.

Similarly 2',2'''-dihydroxy-4, 4', 4'', 4'''-tetramethoxy-3, 3''-bichalconyl (Ib), obtained from 2', 2'-dimethoxy-5',5'-diformylbiphenyl² and 2-hydroxy-4-methoxyacetophenone gave 4', 4'''-7,7'''-tetramethoxy-3',3'''-biflavonyl (IIb) on heating with selenium dioxide. The same biflavonyl was also obtained from 2-hydroxy-4-methoxyacetophenone and 3-iodo-4-methoxy benzaldehyde by the alternative procedure involving Ullmann reaction. The intermediate iodochalcone was also converted into the corresponding flavanone derivative.

2',2'',4',4'', Tetramethoxy and 4',4''',6,6'''-tetramethoxy-3',3'''-biflavonyl (2c and 2d) were similarly synthesised from bichalconyl derivatives (Ic and Id) obtained from the

^aPart VI, this *Journal*, 1965, 42, 435.

1. Mathai and Sethna, this *Journal* 1964, 41, 347.

2. Mathai and Sethna, this *Journal* 1963, 40, 347.

3. Kanakalakshmi, Mathai and Sethna, this *Journal*, in press.

condensation of 2-hydroxyacetophenone with 2, 2', 6, 6'-tetramethoxy-3,3''-diformyl biphenyl⁵ and 2,2',4,4'-tetramethoxy 5,5''-diformylbiphenyl⁵ respectively.

4,4'-D hydroxy-3,3'-diacetylbiphenyl⁴ on condensation with anisaldehyde gave 6,6'''-d hydroxy-4,4''-dimethoxy-3',3'''-bichalconyl which on refluxing with selenium dioxide in amyl alcohol gave 4',4'''-dimethoxy-6,6''-biflavonyl previously prepared by Chen *et al*⁵ by the Ullmann reaction on 4'-methoxy-6-iodoflavone. The bichalconyl was also converted into the corresponding biflavanonyl derivative by refluxing with alcoholic hydrochloric acid.

(I)

(II)

- a : R=OCH₃, R'=H, R''=H, R'''=OCH₃
 b : R=H, R'=OCH₃, R''=H, R'''=OCH₃
 c : R=H, R'=OCH₃, R''=OCH₃, R'''=H
 d : R=OCH₃, R'=OCH₃, R''=H, R'''=H

*EXPERIMENTAL

Chalcones and Bichalconyls.—To a mixture of hydroxyketone and aldehyde (0.01 *M* or 0.02 *M* of each as required) dissolved in alcohol, potassium hydroxide (10 g. in 10 ml. water) was added and the mixture was kept for 24 to 48 hr. in a well stoppered bottle. It was then diluted and acidified with hydrochloric acid. The precipitated chalcone or bichalconyl was then crystallised from a suitable solvent as given in Table I.

*All m.p.s. are uncorrected.

4. Bon-Long, *J. Pharm. Assoc.*, Siam 1948, 1, 5; *Chem. Abst.*, 1949, 49, 5017.

5. Chen, Chang, Hung, Lin, Choong, *Proc. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 232.

Acetoxy-derivative (Table No. II).—The chalcone or bichalconyl derivative was refluxed with acetic anhydride and fused sodium acetate in an oil bath at 140-50° for 2 hr. The mixture was cooled and poured in water and the separated product was crystallised from acetic acid or benzene.

TABLE I

Chalcones and bichalconyls

Name	Solvent	M.P. °C	Yield	Formula	%Carbon Found Req'd.	%Hydrogen Found Req'd.	%Iodine Found Req'd.
2',2'''-Dihydroxy-6,6''-4',4''' tetramethoxy-3,3''-bichalconyl	Nitro benzene	223	55%	C ₃₄ H ₃₀ O ₈	72.4 72.1	5.3 5.3	— —
2',2'''-Dihydroxy-4,4',4'',4'''- tetramethoxy-3,3''-bichalconyl	„	271	60	C ₃₄ H ₃₀ O ₈	71.8 72.1	5.6 5.3	— —
2'-Hydroxy-2,4'-dimethoxy- 5-iodochalcone	Alcohol- Acetone	134	65	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ I O ₄	49.8 49.7	3.5 3.7	30.7 31.0
2'-Hydroxy-4,4'-dimethoxy- 3-iodochalcone	„	163	62	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ I O ₄	49.7 49.7	4.0 3.7	30.9 31.0
2',2'''-Dihydroxy-2,2'',4,4'''- tetramethoxy-3,3''-bichalconyl	Benzene	235	71	C ₃₀ H ₃₀ O ₈	72.0 72.1	5.1 5.3	— —
2',2'''-Dihydroxy-4,4'',6,6'''- tetramethoxy-3,3''-bichalconyl	Xylene	255	53	C ₃₀ H ₃₀ O ₈	72.4 72.1	5.0 5.3	— —
6',6'''-Dihydroxy-4,4''-dimethoxy 3,3'''-bichalconyl	Nitro benzene	224	48	C ₃₂ H ₂₆ O ₆	76.3 76.0	5.0 5.1	— —

TABLE II

Acetoxy derivatives of the chalcones and bichalconyls described in Table I

Name	M.P. °C	Formula	%Carbon Found Req'd.	%Hydrogen Found Req'd.	%Iodine Found Req'd.
2',2'''-Diacetoxy-	182	C ₃₈ H ₃₄ O ₁₀	69.9 70.2	5.5 5.2	— —
2',2'''-Diacetoxy-	160	C ₃₈ H ₃₄ O ₁₀	69.7 70.2	5.5 5.2	— —
2'-Acetoxy-	142	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ I O ₃	50.2 50.4	3.5 3.8	28.4 28.1
2'-Acetoxy-	131	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ I O ₃	50.7 50.4	3.6 3.8	28.0 28.1
2',2'''-Diacetoxy-	155	C ₃₈ H ₃₄ O ₁₀	70.3 70.1	5.3 5.2	— —
2',2'''-Diacetoxy-	212	C ₃₈ H ₃₄ O ₁₀	70.4 70.1	5.1 5.2	— —
6',6'''-Diacetoxy-	170	C ₃₆ H ₃₀ O ₈	72.9 73.2	4.9 5.1	— —

Flavanones and Biflavanonyls (Table No. III).—The chalcone or bichalconyl derivative was refluxed in sufficient alcohol containing conc. HCl for 30 hr. The alcohol was removed by distillation and the resulting mixture was diluted with water and the precipitated flavanone or biflavanonyl derivative was crystallised from a suitable solvent as given in the table.

TABLE III

Flavanones and biflavanonyl of the chalcones and bichalconyls described in Table I

Name	Solvent	M.P. °C	Formula	%Carbon Found	%Carbon Reqd.	%Hydrogen Found	%Hydrogen Reqd.	%Iodine Found	%Iodine Reqd.
7,2'-Dimethoxy-5'-iodoflavanone	Benzene	150	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ IO ₄	49.6	49.8	3.6	3.7	30.6	31.0
7,4'-Dimethoxy-3'-iodoflavanone	Alcohol	143	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ IO ₄	49.7	49.8	3.6	3.7	30.8	31.0
4',4''',6',6'''-Tetramethoxy-3',3'''-biflavanonyl	Xylene	270	C ₃₄ H ₃₀ O ₈	72.2	72.1	5.3	5.3	—	—
4',4'''-Dimethoxy-6,6'''-biflavanonyl	Benzene	250	C ₃₂ H ₂₆ O ₈	76.2	75.9	5.2	5.1	—	—

Flavones and Biflavonyls (Table No. IV). The chalcone or bichalconyl derivative was refluxed with selenium dioxide in amyl alcohol at 140-50° in an oil bath for 15 hr. It was filtered hot. The flavone or biflavonyl derivative separated out either on cooling or on removal of the solvent by steam distillation. The flavones and the biflavonyls were crystallised from the solvent as given in the table.

TABLE IV

Flavones and biflavonyls of the chalcones and bichalconyls described in Table I

Name	Solvent	M.P. °C	Formula	%Carbon Found	%Carbon Reqd.	%Hydrogen Found	%Hydrogen Reqd.	%Iodine Found	%Iodine Reqd.
6',6'''-7,7'''-Tetramethoxy-3',3'''-biflavonyl	Nitro benzene	317	C ₃₄ H ₂₇ O ₈	72.6	72.6	4.6	4.6	—	—
4',4'''-7,7'''-Tetramethoxy-3',3'''-biflavonyl	„	305	C ₃₄ H ₂₆ O ₈	72.5	72.6	5.0	4.6	—	—
7,2'-Dimethoxy-5'-iodoflavone	Benzene	210	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ IO ₄	49.6	50.0	3.6	3.2	31.3	31.1
7,4'-Dimethoxy-3'-iodoflavone*	Toluene	217	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ IO ₄	50.4	50.0	3.7	3.2	30.9	31.1
2',2'''-4',4'''-Tetramethoxy-3',3'''-biflavonyl	Benzene Petroleum ether	215	C ₃₄ H ₂₆ O ₈	72.8	72.6	4.6	4.6	—	—
4',4'''-6',6'''-Tetramethoxy-3',3'''-biflavonyl	Nitro benzene	328	C ₃₄ H ₂₆ O ₈	72.1	72.6	4.5	4.6	—	—
4',4'''-Dimethoxy-6',6'''-biflavonyl	„	318†	C ₃₂ H ₂₆ O ₈	75.4‡	76.5	4.9	4.4	—	—

*Jurd (*Chem. Ind.* 1961,322) who prepared the same compound by another method reported m.p. 219°

† Chen *et al.* gave m.p. 315-20°

‡ Further crystallisation did not improve the analysis.

Ullmann Reaction.—The iodoflavone was mixed with an equal amount of copper bronze and heated at 250-60° in an oil bath for 2 hr. Alternately, the mixture was refluxed in diphenyl ether for 2 hr. In the former, the mixture was extracted with diphenyl ether. In both cases, on removal of the solvent by steam distillation and working up as usual the biflavonyl was obtained.

Thanks of the authors are due to the Government of India for the award of a research training scholarship to K. P. Mathai and to the University Grants Commission for the award of a scholarship to B. Kanakalakshmi.

CHEMISTRY DEPARTMENT,
FACULTY OF SCIENCE,
M.S. UNIVERSITY OF BARODA,
BARODA.

Received August, 16, 1966.